

MODELING THE MOVEMENT OF COTTON SEEDS IN THE LINTING PROCESS AND THEIR MATHEMATICAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract. This scientific article addresses the issues of mathematical modeling and analysis of the movement of cotton seeds in the linting process. The random movement of seeds in the linting chamber is highly complex, and their trajectories can be described by a system of nonlinear differential equations. The Poincaré–Bendixson theorem is applied in the article to determine the existence of isolated periodic trajectories. Based on this mathematical model, the movement of seeds in the linting chamber was analyzed, and the results allowed for the characterization of equilibrium points and closed seed trajectories.

Keywords: linting, seed movement, differential equations, isolated trajectories, Poincaré–Bendixson theorem, mathematical modeling, Lyapunov function, equilibrium point.

The ginning process is a complex and stochastic process associated with the movement of seeds and the separation of fibers from the seed surface. In this process, the movement of the seeds and the fibers on them exhibit a high degree of variability, making it important to use mathematical modeling to analyze the movement of seeds in the working chamber of the gin. To effectively control the movement of seeds during the ginning process, it is necessary to analyze their movement trajectory. This paper presents the mathematical modeling and analysis of the movement of seeds in the gin chamber.

The movement of seeds during the ginning process is irregular and stochastic, with seed rotation and movement relative to the gin blade being key factors. Understanding the movement of seeds requires studying their dynamics, which can be achieved by applying a system of nonlinear differential equations. In this system, the forces and motions at the center of gravity of the seed can be analyzed.

The study involves examining the movement of seeds in the gin chamber and identifying their isolated periodic trajectories. To model the movement of seeds in the gin chamber, we consider the following system of nonlinear differential equations:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dx}{dt} = -y + x(1 - x^2 - y^2) \\ \frac{dy}{dt} = x + y(1 - x^2 - y^2) \end{cases} \quad (2.1)$$

Here, x and y represent the spatial coordinates of the seed, while $f(x,y)$ and $g(x,y)$ are the interaction functions of the seed. To solve this model, we introduce r and θ as polar coordinates. Here, r – radial distance of the seed, and θ – angular coordinate. Then, we have $x = r\cos\theta$ and $y = r\sin\theta$ with $r^2 = x^2 + y^2$ and $\theta = \arctg(\frac{y}{x})$.

In that case, the spatial coordinates take the following form:

$$\begin{cases} x \frac{dx}{dt} + y \frac{dy}{dt} = r \frac{dr}{dt} \\ x \frac{dy}{dt} - y \frac{dx}{dt} = r^2 \frac{d\theta}{dt} \end{cases} \quad (2.2)$$

If we substitute these equations into system (2.1) and calculate their derivatives, we obtain the following equations:

$$r \frac{dr}{dt} = r^2 (1 - r^2) \quad (2.3)$$

Now, if we multiply the second equation of the system by r and the first equation by θ , and then add the results, we get:

$$r \frac{d\theta}{dt} = r^2 \quad (2.4)$$

Each of the equations here is based on the combined state of direction. In this case, the Poincaré – Bendixson theorem can be used to identify isolated periodic trajectories.

System (2.1) has a unique point at $O(0,0)$. Now, since we are only interested in constructing the trajectories, we can assume $r > 0$. Then, taking into account equations (2.3) and (2.4), this means that system (2.1) can be simplified into the following form:

$$r \frac{dr}{dt} = r^2 (1 - r^2), \quad r \frac{d\theta}{dt} = 1 \quad (2.5)$$

Each of the obtained equations in system (2.5) is easily integrated, and the entire family of solutions is given by the following formula:

$$r = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + Ce^{-2t}}}, \quad \theta = t + t_0 \quad (2.6)$$

Alternatively, these can be expressed in the form of the following equations for the variables x and y :

$$x = \frac{A \cos(t + t_0)}{\sqrt{1 + Ce^{-2t}}}, \quad y = \frac{A \sin(t + t_0)}{\sqrt{1 + Ce^{-2t}}} \quad (2.7)$$

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the movement of the seed in a closed contour within the gin chamber.

Suppose we have a bounded region P in motion, which lies in the phase plane along with its boundary and contains no fixed points of system (2.2). Then, by the Poincaré-Bendixson

criterion, it is proven that if the trajectory r of the system (2.2) starts at a point within the region at the initial moment of time and remains entirely within P , then the trajectory r is either itself a closed trajectory or it spirals towards a closed trajectory over time.

We will draw the movement graphs of the seed according to the figure 1 provided. Here, D consists of two closed curves r_1 and r_2 and the annular area between them.

We connect the vector to each boundary point of the domain D :

$$V(x, y) = X(x, y) * i + Y(x, y) * j \quad (2.8)$$

If the trajectory Γ exits from a boundary point at the initial moment $t=t_0$, enters the region D , and remains entirely within it, then according to the above conclusion, the trajectory Γ_1 approaches some closed trajectory Γ_0 located within the region D . In this case, the curve Γ_0 encloses a special point P of the differential system that does not lie within the region D .

The differential system (2.2) provides a simple example of applying the above criterion to find the boundary cycles. Indeed, the system has a single fixed point at $O(0,0)$, and therefore there are no fixed points between the region D and the circles of radius r_1 and r_2 . Based on the first equation of system (2.4), we observe this in the inner and outer circles. The vector V associated with points on the boundary of the region D is always directed inward toward the interior of the region. This implies that within the annular region between the circles r_1 and r_2 , there must be a closed trajectory of the differential system (2.2). Such a closed trajectory exists, and it is the circle of radius r_2 .

However, it should be emphasized that in the general case of systems in the form of (2.2), the practical application of the Poincaré – Bendixson criterion encounters significant difficulties, as there are no general methods for constructing the corresponding domains. Therefore, success depends on both the type of system and the researcher's experience. At the same time, it is important to remember that finding indications of the absence of boundary cycles is no less significant than finding criteria for their existence.

Here, the most common Lyapunov function is considered: if there exists a continuous function $V(x,u)$ with continuous partial derivatives such that it is a positive definite function in some simply connected domain D in the phase plane, then the differential system (2.2) has no boundary cycles within the domain D . When $V(x,u)=1$, it indicates that this relates to its Bendixson criterion.

If we imagine the movement of the seed, it can be expressed by a random function describing trajectories that spiral inward. All of this depends on the trajectory of the movement. As the trajectory progresses, the seeds move unevenly due to their density. They may lag behind or come to a stop, which results in the slipping of the seed on the gin, leading to the removal of the fiber from the seed.

Based on the Poincaré – Bendixson theorem, the existence of closed trajectories in the phase space is determined. As a result of solving nonlinear differential systems based on a mathematical model, isolated periodic solutions for the movement of seeds are found. Based on these solutions, the movement trajectories of the seeds in the gin chamber are analyzed using the approach of convergence, and characteristic closed trajectories for nonlinear systems in the phase space are identified.

Conclusion:

It is necessary to use nonlinear differential equations to describe the movement of seeds in the ginning process and model their trajectories.

As a result of mathematical modeling, the movement of seeds in the gin chamber is analyzed through randomly isolated periodic trajectories.

The equilibrium points in the movement of seeds and their isolated trajectories are identified using nonlinear differential systems.

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